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Using English as a foreign language when teaching subjects of the criminal law cycle

NATALIA SEMCHUK^{1*}, SOFIIA LYKHOVA¹
and ULIYA DEMIANENKO²

The paper analysed the experiences in a field of teaching Criminal Law cycle subjects in English. The research was held at the National Aviation University (Kyiv, Ukraine) and involved 11 first-year students and 11 second-year students majoring in “Jurisprudence” who study full-time (teaching is conducted in English). The purpose of the paper was to study the formation of foreign language competence by students-lawyers at the same time as the formation of general legal competences in teaching a foreign language. At the same time, the students must operate the English terminology and know the theoretical approaches to problems in English-speaking countries. After establishing the appropriate psychological and pedagogical conditions, the number of students in the experimental group having the productive and creative levels of readiness to use English in their professional activity has significantly increased compared to the control group.

Keywords: assessment, criminal legal disciplines, motivation, English-speaking countries

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INTRODUCTION

The subjects of the criminal law cycle occupy a special place in the preparation of specialists from three specialties – “International Law”, “Law Enforcement” and “Jurisprudence”. The goal of teaching “Criminal Law” is mastering theoretical knowledge in the field of criminal law and strengthening of practical skills to apply them in specific situations, the formation of legal culture in the practical application of the criminal law. The tasks of studying the discipline are: study of legislative and other normative legal acts regulates legal relations in the field of crime and punishment, studying the basic institutions and concepts of criminal law, and skills acquisition of theoretical knowledge in practice (Eshun & Amoako-Agyeman 2016, Annamalah et al. 2016, Wellham 2016, Petrovic 2016, Petrosyan 2016a, 2016b; Vansover 2016, Schoeneman & Sawyer 2016, Ojha 2016, O'Brien & Adam 2016a, 2016b; Lynch & Smith 2016a, 2016b; Carter & Francis 2016, Dhakal & Pant 2016, McAuliffe 2016, Smith 2016, Millear 2016, Lynch et al. 2016, Doe 2016).

One of these techniques is the Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). With regard to the content of CLIL, the scope of the subject and linguistic content can vary in one way or another, creating content-led and language-led models. When designing a course based on the CLIL method, a person must take into account 4 Cs: *Content* – development and acquisition of new knowledge, skills, subject area skills; *Communication* – learning to use the language to acquire knowledge; *Cognition* – development of cognitive and mental abilities, solving problem situations; *Culture* – identification of a part of culture, with the awareness of the existence of an alternative culture, that is, the path to intercultural understanding (Coyle et al. 2010). But the use of such a technique should correspond to the language policy of the university and be laid already at the level of the curriculum.

Not looking at the fact that the National Aviation University has been training foreign languages for more than 30 years, so far this system cannot be implemented as a whole due to the specific requirements for the curriculum. In addition, in general, this system does not take into account the specificity of the lawyer's training. But some of its elements have an emphasis on teaching lawyers in an foreign language. Legal education is a broad concept. It includes training professionals for practicing in courts, law teaching, law research, administration in different areas, legal consulting in commercial and industrial companies and other activities which postulate and require legal knowledge and skills (Vinnichenko & Gladun 2018). The core objective of legal education in universities is to enable students to get the essential legal competencies and skills, formalizing this process by gaining official certification. It is a necessary requirement for admission to certain types of legal practice (i.e. an advocate or a judge).

The law schools are required to equip their graduates not only with contemporary theoretical knowledge of law but also with enhanced practical skills, which are necessary for lawyers, judges and professionals in related fields to act effectively in a globalized context. The globalization of legal education has a significant relationship with legal practice in a globalized context. This study specifically examined and focused on the pathways to admission and the

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process through which the lawyers are licensed by evaluating the practical skills incorporated into the school curriculum (Yu et al. 2018).

In the era of European integration, the role of English language acquisition is increasing for these specialists as well. Teaching subjects of the criminal law cycle in English is by its nature multidimensional and interdisciplinary. With regard to the use of pedagogical developments in this area it is worth noting that the Faculty of Law belongs to the faculties, which are most often chosen for the study of students with disabilities and teachers are ready to teach them a course with definite peculiarities (Colyn 2017). At the same time, there are the next types of training activities accepted under the obligations of training activities accepted under the obligations of continuous or specialization training for law students: Attending face to face training sessions, Completing distance training sessions, Completing e-learning modules, Watching a webinar, Completing blended learning activities, Attending training conferences, Participating in training activities as trainer or teacher, Writing and Publishing (Fernando & Perez 2018).

Ukrainian law schools should also focus on the possibility of training students with disabilities and the widespread use of multimedia and distance learning to compensate for special educational needs. The first aspect of this phenomenon is that such teaching is part of legal education, and in its study it is necessary to take into account the current trends in this field. At the present stage, many researchers are paying attention to certain aspects of legal education. Thus, the researchers draw attention to the development of certain aspects of legal education, which are important and for the teaching of the lawful disciplines in a foreign language. For example, the need to pay more attention to the development of basic skills such as research, reading and writing (Colgan et al. 2017); the need for wider use of legal experiments in the training of lawyers (Jun Ping 2012); the importance of subject orientation, standardization of legal education, raising the level of legal education and regulating the management of legal education (Li 2018). Also, researchers pay attention to a number of universal deficiencies in legal education. Among such problems is the emergence of legal schools with low cost of tuition and unsatisfactory level of teaching (Tejani 2018); the historical influence of legal centralism and positivism (Himonga & Diallo 2017), a shortage of applied disciplines that are on the verge of providing LLB and greatly affect socio-legal research (Brooman 2017) and a great inspiration for learning such general legal categories of fundamental rights and obligations and justice (Hazat 2018). Except for the category of Justice, subcategories relevant to the primary categories were mentioned by more participants at the end of the semester”.

As can be seen from the analysis of these studies, the issues of legal educations are the object of attention of scholars from around the world, but mainly explore some aspects of legal education. The issue of teaching certain legal subjects in a foreign language has not yet been the subject of active study by scientists (Willis et al. 2018, Eshun et al. 2018, Swaroop & Dixit 2018, Wu et al. 2018, Kamel & Watfa 2018, Knezovic & Musrati 2018, Tahirsylaj et al. 2018, Prior 2018, Narayan 2018, Venkateswaran & Vincent 2018, Siddins 2018, Carter 2018, Moir et al. 2018, Peel et al. 2018, Pearson & Athota 2018, Carter & Goldie 2018, Daniel 2018, Novitasari

& Yusuf 2018, Nuhayatie 2018, Elisondo 2018, Vansover 2018, Chougule 2018, Lynch et al. 2018, Al-Qatawneh & Al-Qatawneh 2018, Trevallion 2018, Ramkumar & Rajini 2018a, 2018b; Pulla 2018, McWaters & Hawkins 2018, Le & Chen 2018, Mungai 2018, Salim 2018, Frederico et al. 2018, Sharma 2018, Bhattacharyya 2018, Hawkins & McWaters 2018).

The second aspect, which is important in the study of the teaching of legal disciplines in a foreign language, is the use of the philological sources themselves in the educational process. The problems of foreign language training raise a great interest in the European educational space. Also, when teaching a foreign language, there are many methodological problems. In this case, the teachers who work on such a program are not philologists. They are professional lawyers with an additional knowledge of English (such as certificates B2 of the CEFR levels). English here serves as a learning tool. Meanwhile, questions arose about the fact that the program of the Faculty of Law and the Faculty of International Relations in this case became very close. Language to a certain extent is a working tool of a lawyer. At the same time, the use of language as a working tool by philologists and lawyers is different. The complexities that arise during the teaching process are also different. The key to philology disciplines is the understanding of the basics of phonetics, grammar, word formation, and others. The basis for lawyers in the mentioned above issue is the understanding and the use of words as terms in different languages and the relationship between them. That is, for the philologist speech serves as the object of study, and for a lawyer, it is a method of cognition. In this case, both philologists and lawyers focus their work on analyzing texts or oral speeches. In practice, these cause some difficulties in teaching legal disciplines in English. After all, philologists do not have the necessary knowledge of subjects taught by lawyers for future lawyers. At the same time, not all lawyers have sufficient level of language training (Garrigan 2017, Pendery 2017, Lynch et al. 2017, Knight & Galletly 2017, Pulla et al. 2017, Jiang & Smith 2017, Doe et al. 2017, Whiting 2017, Madden 2017a, 2017b; Daniel & Johnstone 2017, Hawkins et al. 2017, Kampel et al. 2017, Parker 2017, Herbert 2017, Boon et al. 2017, Ranatunga & Pagliano 2017, Carter et al. 2017, Carter & Goldie 2017, Campbell & Narayan 2017, Pulla 2017, Mukhopadhyay & Saha 2017, Vansover 2017, Sellars 2017, Muñoz-Blanco & Vargas 2017, Lynch & Madden 2017, Strydom 2017, Wagner 2017).

Comparison in the process of teaching with other countries has a number of difficulties. First of all, English is a working language in more than 30 countries. Among them are not only Canada, Great Britain, the USA, but also, for example, Ghana, Mauritius and Singapore. All these English-speaking countries use unequal legal terminology. At the same time, most of these countries belong to the common law system. For example, some countries use the term “barrister”, and the other countries use the term “attorney-at-law” in the same sense as the “advocate”. The second problem is that Ukraine’s legislation has long evolved in isolation from global trends. This led to the fact that in Criminal Law there are institutes that do not have foreign analogues. Therefore, we must achieve two goals. Learn the fundamentals of Criminal Law in Ukraine and learn the relevant terminology in English. At the same time, English terminology is not unified because there are many English-

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speaking countries with different legislation. And several synonymous or similar terms may be used to refer to one phenomenon. To solve these problems we need to use special resources. First of all, we should use special resources for translators. Secondly, we need Ukrainian legislation (for example, the Criminal Code of Ukraine in English). Today in our country, there are more than a hundred thousand normative legal acts. At the same time, only about one of them is available officially or high-quality translated. In this case, even the available translated texts are not amended in line with changes in the legislation.

The purpose of the paper was to study the formation of foreign language competence by students-lawyers at the same time as the formation of general legal competences in teaching foreign language. The tasks needed to implement the purpose are the following: to analyze the necessity of using different types of scientific and methodological literature on the issues of forming foreign language competence; to define the characteristic features in teaching students of the Faculty of Law with English language teaching using different teaching methods in the educational environment of the university, and to determine the pedagogical conditions for developing future lawyers readiness to use English in their professional activity by testing methodology of the formation of the foreign language competence for students of the Faculty of Law with English language teaching. On the basis of the analysis of the concept and structure of foreign language competence of professionals in different areas, it is established that in modern pedagogical literature there is no common understanding of the essence of foreign language competence. "Foreign language competence" is a complex and multi-faceted scientific concept. Summarizing various scientific theoretical approaches, we formulate "foreign language competence" as a dynamic combination of knowledge, practical skills. Foreign language competence determines the ability of individuals to use a foreign language in professional, scientific activities and in social communication successfully (Stavytska 2017).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the purpose of completeness, the study involved a survey of students of our English-language program. On the first year of study, we had 11 students, on the second -11, in the total of 22. The standard deviation (SD) was calculated by the formula (1) Sample Standard Deviation:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (1)$$

where: \bar{x} is the sample average AVERAGE VALUE (number 1, number 2, ...), and n is the sampling size (22 students). $SD = 8.08$. The median for the sample was 11, 5. The mode of a data set (the number that occurs most frequently in the set) is 17.

The equation (2) for VARP was:

$$\sum (x - \bar{x})^2 \frac{1}{n}, \quad (2)$$

where: n is the sample size. $VARP = 6.25$.

Students of the English-language project study were in two groups: 106 (first year) and 206 (2nd year). The research was carried out in the first and second semesters of the 2019 school year. The survey was conducted after the session in the first semester (in the middle of the study). As an objective criterion, data about academic success of students of 106 and 206 groups (English-language project, experimental group) and other groups of the first and second courses were used. The average age of students was 17 years. Among students, 70% are males, 30% are females. All except one student are citizens of Ukraine (95.5%) and previously did not study in other universities (95.5%). Most students chose the Law Faculty of NAU through an English-language program (80%).

In order to understand the effectiveness of teaching, the reporting data on the consolidated success of students of English and Ukrainian-speaking groups was used. It is worth noting that in Ukraine to assess the current performance of students during the semester, a 5-point system was used, where 2 is the worst score and 5 is an excellent result. For the final assessment, the pan-European ECTS scale is used. For the first semester, the average success rate of the judges of the 106 groups of subjects in the criminal law cycle was 4.2 (the average success of the judges of 101-105 groups was 4.1); for the second semester – 4.27 (the average success of the judges of 101-105 groups was 4.15). During the first semester, the average success rate of the judges of the 206 groups of subjects in the criminal law cycle was 4.3 (the average success of the judges of 101-105 groups was 4.25); for the second semester – 4.31 (the average success of the judges of 101-105 groups was 4.21). The data indicate the overall effectiveness of the methods used and the overall good level of knowledge of students of the English-language project. During the study, we used a questionnaire to identify students' attitudes towards the use of the special courses.

Anonymous questionnaire included 4 open and 5 closed questions. Closed questions related to gender, age, group, course, etc. The open questions were as follows: Did you like the course? If yes, what particularly did you like about it? What difficulties did you have in learning the course? Why did you choose NAU? Where do you plan to work in the future?

The anonymous student survey showed the following trends. All except one student are citizens of Ukraine, and previously did not study in other universities. Most students liked the course (95%). The main difficulty is the need to use a large number of heterogeneous sources (65 %).

Most students chose the Law Faculty of NAU through an English-language program (70%), on the advice of parents (20%); could not answer 10%. At the same time, most students in the future see themselves as employees of international law firms or barristers (65 %). However, some students see themselves as judges (10%), prosecutors (10%) and politicians (10%) in the future; could not answer 5%.

As the research results show, most students of the English-language program of the Law Faculty of NAU are Ukrainian citizens who want to combine -studying of Law and English language. These are young people under 20 years of age.

To achieve the purpose of the research the complex methods were used:

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▪1. **Theoretical methods:** analysis, synthesis, systematization and generalization of scientific data contained in pedagogical, philosophical and methodological literature, legal acts in the field of higher education to determine the state of the research problem and identify the pedagogical conditions of teaching criminal legal disciplines in English (curriculum, plans, tutorials, textbooks, audio- and video materials, etc); interdisciplinary synthesis; systematisation of theoretical data, etc; generalisation of pedagogical experience for making conclusions and recommendations for the efficient use in classroom, etc.

▪ 2. **Empirical methods:** tests, interviews, surveys of students and teachers for primary empirical research.

While researching the use of different methods in teaching legal disciplines in a foreign language, which is not the official language of the state, a set of methods was used: (a) *theoretical methods:* a systematic and comparative analysis of psychological and pedagogical, methodical, scientific literature on the research issues; an analysis of existing teaching materials used to train future lawyers (curriculum, plans, tutorials, textbooks, audio- and video materials, etc); interdisciplinary synthesis; systematization of theoretical data, etc.; generalization of pedagogical experience for making conclusions and recommendations for the efficient use etc.; (b) *empirical methods:* tests, questionnaires, interviews, participant observation in the educational process, etc.

The research was held on the basis of the National Aviation University and enrolled 22 undergraduate students majoring in “Jurisprudence”. The pedagogical experiment was conducted in two stages. At the first stage, we aimed at determining the state of the problem by using tests, questionnaires and interviews as well as analysing documentation, teaching materials and methods, considering the results of final tests, credits, examinations, etc. The analysis of the results showed generally good English communication skills for the effective professional activity and revealed its causes: sufficient English level of the first-year students after school; generally good knowledge of specialized subjects; in general, sufficient amount of hours for classroom work; lack of ICT in teaching, etc. The main reason for such a generally good situation with foreign language proficiency is the strict selection of admissions when enrolling in the English-language project and the small number of students in the group (11 persons), which allows the teacher to pay more attention to the student.

The introduction of reasonable pedagogical conditions to improve students’ English language proficiency and general legal skills in the system of higher legal education and stimulate them for lifelong learning involved the implementation of the second (formative) stage of the experiment: (1) enhancing students’ internal motivation to intellectual activity and further self-education; (2) content and language integrated learning (CLIL), and (3) developing and implementing multilevel tasks in the educational process using ICT. To determine the level of students’ motivation, we used the survey method (including questionnaires, interviews with students). We developed a multilevel complex of exercises based on using case-study method, brainstorming and discussions. At this stage, two groups were formed: an experimental group (EG) included 22 first and second-year students and a control

group (CG) included the same number of students majoring in “Jurisprudence” who study full-time (135 first-year students with Ukrainian language learning and 120 second-year students with Ukrainian language learning). Other conditions for both groups were approximately the same: the higher educational institution; topics of the syllabus and hours for classroom study and self-study, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research was carried out to examine how students perceive the implementation of studying legal disciplines in a foreign language, which is not the official language of the state. The first is the need to increase the number of foreign students. The second is the need for national lawyers who can work with in-house counterparts.

At the same time, the curriculum for students with Ukrainian and English language instruction contains the same number of academic hours. It concerns simultaneously at the same time philology, pedagogy and law.

However, the analysis of previous research on the problem has shown that still there is a research gap in studying legal disciplines in a foreign language, which is not the official language of the state.

We have developed a practical tool that combines philological, pedagogical, and law techniques. It is based on literature from all three directions. At the current level of international cooperation and economic development, English language knowledge comes to the forefront of a lawyer. It cannot always be regarded as a separate competence, but it becomes a basic component of the legal profession.

The first one is the need to develop a very large number of training programs. These programs are quite complicated for a number of reasons. These programs should be integrated.

They should contain the basic theoretical provisions of national science and practice and comparison with English-speaking countries and terminology explanation. At the same time, they must as a whole be consistent with programs of non-integrated nature, at least by the number of training hours.

Therefore, the National Aviation University, among the faculties where the English language teaching program was introduced, was chosen a legal department.

Therefore, the English-language teaching program among other faculties of National Aviation University has been chosen for the introduction and development by the Faculty of Law too. There are first and second-year students in English-language groups. The quantity of the students in every group is about 11. Unfortunately, the NAU has not gotten yet an accredited English-language Master’s degree in law. Today, the department provides teaching of the following courses: “Organization of Judicial and Law Enforcement Bodies”, “Prosecution of Ukraine” and “Criminal law”. Today, Criminal Law and Process Department provides teaching of the following courses: “Organization of Judicial and Law Enforcement Bodies”, “Prosecution of Ukraine” and “Criminal law”. In the future, the department also plans to teach such courses as: “Preparation of Notaries Procedural Documents”, “Prosecutor’s Supervision”, “Advocacy and Notary Service in Ukraine”, “Comparative Criminal Law”, “Problems of Criminal and Legal

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Protection of Human and Citizen Rights”. The goal of teaching “Criminal Law” is mastering theoretical knowledge in the field of criminal law and strengthening of practical skills to apply them in specific situations, the formation of legal culture in the practical application of the criminal law. The tasks of studying the discipline are: study of legislative and other normative legal acts regulating legal relations in the field of crime and punishment, studying the basic institutions and concepts of criminal law, skills acquisition of theoretical knowledge in practice.

As an example, all modules include: reading activity; language in use; a glossary; a forum, and a quiz. This system has a wide range of components; the decision to use any of them was made when a particular course was being studied. This provides flexibility possibility to start using the system from any component (e.g., a forum, a glossary, a lesson, etc.) but gradually add other components. Fernando and Perez (2018) highlighted the next types of training activities accepted under the obligations of continuous or specialization training for law students: Attending face to face training sessions, Completing distance training sessions, Completing e-learning modules, Watching a webinar, Completing blended learning activities, Attending training conferences, Participating in training activities as trainer or teacher, Writing and Publishing.

With this view, you can fully agree. Approximately, the assessment of skills and knowledge of students in the curricula of the National Aviation University was carried out. The analysis of the responses in the questionnaire with open-ended questions revealed that students had positive perceptions:

- the students were enthusiastic about learning and had a strong motivational component;
- respondents could apply the acquired knowledge in more effective manner (operational component);
- students developing presentation skills (organizational and technological component), and
- participants worked together to achieve their common goals (social and personality component).

In fact, students learn more effectively when they are actively engaged in classroom activities and self-study process by having discussions, interacting with peers and teachers, analyzing and critically evaluating information. These skills are highly required for their future professional activity. Moreover, the best combination of teaching, philological, foreign criminal law and domestic legal sources in the process of teaching is combined. Studying according to an English-speaking program requires knowledge of legal disciplines, knowledge of legal terminology and a high level of English language proficiency.

While the teaching of Criminal Law cycle subjects has a significant specificity. First of all, this is a problem with textbooks for teaching. At the same time, there is a fundamentally different understanding of the basic provisions of Criminal Law in Ukraine and the Anglo-Saxon countries. This can be shown on the example of complicity. In Ukraine, an organizer, an abettor and an accessory, together with a principal offender, are deemed to be accomplices in a criminal offence. In common law system, the following terms are used: principal in the First Degree; principal

in the Second Degree; accessory before the fact; accessory after the fact. It is necessary to combine these two approaches within one lecture.

In this case, English-language vocabulary will be suitable only for the system of common law. For an adequate translation into the Ukrainian language, further amendments and clarifications are needed. The main reason for this is that the phenomena that need to be described in terms are not available in English-speaking countries as such.

Another problem is that English is an official language in more than 30 countries. All these countries have different legal regulations. They also use different vocabulary and terms. An example of such plurality of terms may be the term “Prosecutor General of Ukraine”. According to the site, it is the official name of the position in Ukraine. At the same time, foreign lawmakers use the following terms as a synonym: Prosecutor-General, Judge Advocate General, Attorney-General, Director of Public Prosecutions, and Chief State Prosecutor. As for other terms, more synonyms can be used.

Davies (2018) indicated that “For legal academia there is no equivalent formal qualifying route, as there is no professional body akin to the Bar Standards Board (BSB) or SRA to set a minimum standard. What is required is entirely dependent upon what individual employing universities look for. From the perspective of accessibility, the purpose of this section is to consider whether, in the absence of a formally defined qualification route for academic ‘professional’ status, there has been an increase over time in the amount of time and money prospective academics have to invest in their education and training to secure the chance to realistically compete for a position in a university law school”.

The lecturer uses three types of materials in preparation for the lecture: terminology textbooks; textbooks on the subject in English and textbooks published in Ukraine and domestic laws.

Terminology textbooks in the field of jurisprudence have their own specifics. Among the most used can be highlighted “English for Legal Professionals” (Frost 2009), “Career Paths: Law” (Evans et al. 2015) and *Introduction to International Legal English* (Krois-Linder 2009). Only one of them – “Career Paths: Law” (Evans et al. 2015) has a little article about Criminal Law. Other textbooks have a pronounced civil law deviation. They do not have sections about the criminal legal terminology.

Fletcher (2007) used systematic emphasis on the relationship between language and legal theory; there is no comparable comparative study of legal language. Therefore, it is basically necessary to use interpretive dictionaries (Hughes 2004) and special systems such as multitrans for the proper use of the terminology.

Textbooks on the subject in English. Because of differences in theoretical approaches, the basics are comparative criminal law textbooks. Dubber and Hernle (2014) examined the language barrier in the context of Criminal Law.

Textbooks published in Ukraine and domestic laws mostly unacceptable in English. There are also no integrated textbooks that outline Ukrainian approaches in comparison with the approaches of the English-speaking countries. Therefore,

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preparing for lectures, the teacher is forced to translate enormous amount of information.

To search for legislation in English, we use the Sherlock database (Sharing Electronic Resources and Laws on Crime 2019). However, only about 28 acts are available for Ukraine (Criminal Code of the Republic of Ukraine, Law on the Protection of Archeological Heritage, Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Ukraine, Law of Ukraine on combating organized crime).

However, even in existing translations of legislative acts, there are no recent changes. For example, the Criminal Code of Ukraine is available in 2001 edition. A teacher should keep track of all the changes, translate them and bring them to the attention of the students on their own. However, most acts, for example, the Law of Ukraine “About Prosecutor’s Office” also have to be translated. Therefore, the main source of information is lectures, prepared by a teacher him/herself.

At the same time, we are trying to implement modern methods for practical classes. Practical training goes in two directions. It is important for a future lawyer to consolidate the theoretical knowledge during seminars, discussion debates, and be able to solve specific cases.

Qi (2018) emphasized that “The emergence of e-learning created new education and diverse environment, conforming to the rapid change in modern society. The high acquisition characteristic breaks through the restrictions to time and space of traditional teaching, and the international emphasis on the problem and development of intellectual property is thoroughly presented on various international conferences and international conventions. The practice on education promotion could enhance the understanding of intellectual property and present the mission to practice intellectual property law, i.e. effectively transforming learners to further enhance the concept of intellectual property” (Qi 2018).

In this case, not only domestic examples from judicial practice, but also foreign countries are used. Problem solving is based largely on real examples of practice. At that, the decision often takes place in two versions – according to the Ukrainian legislation and the American one. The curriculum for the number of hours and issues that are recommended for study is broadly identical to the Ukrainian-language and English-speaking groups. Since the use of both Ukrainian and foreign textbooks is possible in different proportions, different ratios of these sources were used during the experiment. During personal communication with students, it was discovered that the best model was the use of national legislation in the translation of a foreign language, foreign sources and philological literature in the following proportion: national legislation in the translation of a foreign language –80%; foreign sources – 15%; philological literature –5% (with an obligatory representation of the glossary at the end of the lecture).

At the same time, the use of real cases from Ukrainian and foreign practices did not show any particular differences (since one and the same situation can be solved from the standpoint of different legal systems), they are used in the ratio of 50/50.

CONCLUSION

The necessity and efficiency of using four types of sources for the training of the teacher to the classes have been confirmed. They are terminology textbooks; textbooks on the subject in English and textbooks published in Ukraine and domestic laws. Studying according to an English-speaking program requires knowledge of legal disciplines, knowledge of legal terminology and a high level of English language proficiency. The results of the experiment prove that students increase their professional competence that positively influences their future professional development and knowledge of a foreign language. Most students liked the course (95%). The main difficulty is the need to use a large number of heterogeneous sources (65%). Most students chose the Law Faculty of NAU through an English-language program (70%), on the advice of parents (20%), and could not answer 10%. At the same time, most students in the future see themselves as employees of international law firms or barristers (65%). However, some students see themselves as judges (10%), prosecutors (10%), politicians (10%) in the future and could not answer 5%.

RECOMMENDATION

During personal communication with students, it was discovered that the best model was the use of national legislation in the translation of a foreign language, foreign sources and philological literature in the following proportion: national legislation in the translation of a foreign language –80%; foreign sources –15% and philological literature –5% (with an obligatory representation of the glossary at the end of the lecture). At the same time, the use of real cases from Ukrainian and foreign practices did not show any particular differences (since one and the same situation can be solved from the standpoint of different legal systems), they are used in the ratio of 50/50. The introduction of modern methods of practical classes and the use of multimedia is also pleasing to students and helps to increase the level of proficiency.

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Development: Trends, Issues &
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